

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *A methodological approach based on combining many previously identified components into a system education with holistic properties and patterns is presented. Also, an integrative approach to learning is implemented through integration processes.*

Keywords: *integrative process, system analysis, educational process, interdisciplinary.*

In the conditions of rapidly changing content of knowledge, their constant growth at an ever-increasing pace, Higher school reform is being carried out in all countries. Here are its main directions: continuity; diversification; fundamentalization;

Today, a specialist is a person with extensive general and special knowledge, able to respond to changes in technology and science that meet the requirements of new technologies that will inevitably be implemented; he needs basic knowledge, problems, analytical thinking, socio-psychological competence, intellectual culture.

The need to consolidate homogeneous, heterogeneous, mixed areas of professional activity, solved tasks, functions, types, interdisciplinary knowledge, skills and abilities is determined by objective processes:

integrative processes in science, education, culture and, accordingly, in professional activity;

strengthening of systemic, synthetic approaches to the study of natural phenomena and the life of society;

strengthening the integration of interdisciplinary knowledge);

strengthening the fundamentalization of specialist training;

raising the importance of the methodological function of vocational training [1].

In these conditions, the holistic nature and content of higher military education are predetermined by changes in life itself, the content and structure of professional activity, its functions and tasks.

Integrative processes change the structure of the content of professional activity, are characterized by a complex of functions included in an integrated profession, their combination, a change in the traditional content, the redistribution of functions and the emergence of new combinations, combinations, expansion of the socio-cultural base of qualifications and professional competence of a modern specialist.

The quality of professional training of a specialist is determined not only by knowledge and skills, but also by the level of mastery of professional activity, the ability to solve complex professional tasks.

Today, a vocational higher education institution is not yet at its best developing the needs of using the potential of fundamental sciences, it does not provide them in sufficient volume

The breadth and depth of fundamental vocational education in general. The problem is that a future specialist must have the skills and professional mobility to respond quickly to the constantly occurring changes in practical and scientific activities, public practice in general. This

will be possible if the university equips the graduate with a general comprehensive (interdisciplinary) methodology of professional activity. In other words, he prepares the "apparatus" of each discipline as a specialist methodologist who knows how to use it in integrative communication with others, as a means of solving problems in cognitive and professional activities.

To do this, firstly, it is necessary to develop and move to a scientifically based concept of interdisciplinary integration that meets the requirements of the objective law of qualitative development of education. Secondly, to create an educational and methodological mechanism for the comprehensive training and retraining of teachers and the creative implementation of this concept in the practice of the university.

The systematic (profile-disciplinary) analysis of the problem includes two closely interrelated stages:

a) analysis and construction of appropriate disciplinary "portraits" of the problem solving process from the perspective of each discipline related to this task;

c) unification (unification) of disciplinary "portraits" into a holistic model of the problem solving process.

In the didactic concept of interdisciplinary integration, the creation of holistic solutions to problems in the cognitive professional activity of students and graduates is considered as a decisive criterion for the practical implementation of interdisciplinary integration (MDI) in education. And systematic (interdisciplinary) analysis as a scientific and practical means of its implementation in the practice of the university.

At the same time, the student's ability to create an appropriate disciplinary "portrait" of the problem-solving process is considered as a criterion of his ability to implement the MD of this subject, to demand and use the knowledge of the subject. Finally, as a form of realization of the qualitative contribution of each department to the training of a specialist.

Thus, the essence, objective functions and purpose of the MDI is to ensure the educational level of students and graduates in each discipline of the curriculum that meets their needs in the ability to create holistic (qualitative) solutions to problems, to implement qualitative solutions in further cognitive and professional activities. In the language of qualimetry, this means that the implementation of MDI ensures the quality of continuing education in the preparation of specialists for graduation and postgraduate education. All this in general gives every reason to consider MDI as the basis of quality education in Higher education.

Given the interdisciplinary integration, a new, broader and deeper approach to the development of educational goals for each discipline of the curriculum is needed.

The main task of education in any subject is to teach students the need and skills to use its scientific content to develop a disciplined and holistic picture of the process of solving cognitive and professional tasks. This implies the specific target functions of various groups of academic subjects.

For fundamental sciences, it is the study of a holistic solution using these disciplines or modeling of a professional problem, that is, the identification of a disciplinary component of the solution, its implementation and preparation for integration into a holistic solution with components of other disciplines.

For profilers, this is training in research aimed at combining the results of the disciplinary stages of direct solution into a single system, i.e. preparing graduates for the integrated use of knowledge of all studied disciplines in the complex solution of cognitive and professional tasks.

Interdisciplinary integration is the educational processes of integration (integration) of academic disciplines into the holistic study (solution) of cognitive and professional problems in graduate and postgraduate education. In general, the MDI mechanism consists in the preparation and real implementation of knowledge (especially in fundamental sciences) in the practice of solving cognitive and professional tasks.

It should be noted that MDI is pedagogical integration, which has fundamental characteristics and differs from integration in science. Their essence is as follows [2].

Interdisciplinary integration:

- ◆ Integration according to the ultimate goal of education: training of a modern specialist; integration of disciplines into the design process, forecasting the results of the educational process and its implementation;

- the work is carried out not only on goals, but also on the technologies to achieve them;

- integration in the process of formation of interdisciplinary skills of students, comprehensive requirement and use of the "apparatus" of disciplines to create disciplinary and holistic solutions to problems;

This is a holistic, as well as end-to-end integration, that is, it is carried out by all departments using all disciplines of the curriculum necessary to create a holistic solution to a specific target problem.

In general, MDI is a synthesis of knowledge, beliefs and practical actions at all stages and levels of continuing education.

Cognition and implementation of problem-solving processes proceeds dynamically in two different, but organically related forms: differentiation - identification and construction of disciplinary components of the decision-making process; integration - synthesis of disciplinary components into an integral system of the problem-solving process.

The long-standing differentiation in science - the division of its individual fields into independent branches - is reflected in the learning process [3]. Differentiation of educational knowledge, carried out everywhere-both in secondary educational institutions and in higher educational institutions, is necessary, since such a separation of the phenomena of objective reality makes it possible to achieve a deep understanding of its individual sides. Differentiation of the educational process in practice is manifested in the study by students of individual scientific and cognitive complexes-academic disciplines, each of which, within the framework of its allocated functional capabilities, represents in a didactically revised form a particular area of scientific knowledge. At the same time, it is believed that the differentiated presentation of scientific knowledge without any evidence provides adequate theoretical and practical training of a young specialist [2]. At the same time, it is known that life and practice dictate and require young people to acquire skills of independent or better creative thinking while studying at school and then at university. This requirement consists in the fact that most practical tasks that people solve require the ability to apply knowledge in a complex, i.e. ni.ba 'zan involves, unites, collects a large number of different components of scientific knowledge related to very distant fields of science [4].

The one-sidedness of differentiation in the educational process and its absence for the preparation of a future specialist have long been noticed by scientists and teachers. In the history

of pedagogical teachings, we probably will not find a single progressive pedagogical science that would not protest against the mandatory separation of academic disciplines that arose in our time as a result of the process of differentiation of the educational and cognitive complex of knowledge called the fundamentals of science. The history of science shows that a category reflecting processes opposite to differentiation, in which integration is always present. With the development of science, the integrative trends of interaction and interpenetration of various fields of knowledge became more and more pronounced.

Currently, integration is becoming a model for the development of social systems. Pedagogy is no exception here, integrative research is carried out most intensively in it. You no longer find educational institutions where they are not engaged in the development of integrated programs, courses. Much in this area is done through intuition, i.e. by trial and error. There are very few practical recommendations on integration, mainly due to the complexity of the research topic. There are many questions in the integral problem of pedagogy that have yet to be studied. In particular, in the methodology and technology of pedagogical integration.

The methodology is a fairly general approach to a specific phenomenon. The exception is the methodological part of the methodology-a set of research methods and techniques. Technology, on the contrary, serves to concretize these approaches. Methodology indirectly influences the objects of theory and practice, while technology plays the role of their direct converter and transformer [4].

Integrative methodology in some way forms a pyramid of two stages of problems. The first OS has problems with determining the critical characteristics of integration. Secondly, the answers are questions that allow us to determine adequate methods for studying integration [5].

The central problem of the critical order is the definition of specificity, i.e. the essence of pedagogical integration. As elsewhere, pedagogical research basically repeats three schemes for determining integration:

- integration is the process of forming integrity.;
- integration is the result of the formation of integrity;
- integration is the process and result of the formation of integrity.

The existing experience in the development of integrative courses and programs allows us to determine a number of its links:

- a) definition of integration goals;
- b) definition of integration objects and components;
- C) separation of the integral connection;
- D) establishment of new links and mediation between the objects and components of integration;
- f) testing of the newly created system [5].

Integration takes place at all levels of pedagogical theory and practice: methodically, in which the synthesis of pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical methods is carried out. As a result, psychological-pedagogical, technical-pedagogical and other disciplines, courses, disciplines are formed.

pedagogical theories and concepts are synthesized at the theoretical level.;

At the practical level, the integration of educational content components is mainly observed in the work-the creation of integrated courses [6].

Methodological and historical-pedagogical analysis of the preparation of specialists for professional activity, the study of the existing modern pedagogical system of training students in higher educational institutions show that at present a significant restructuring of the educational process in a higher military educational institution is necessary. The essence of higher education must be constantly redefined by life.

During the training, there is a systematic collection, processing and use of "different" information, which creates prerequisites for the consolidation of knowledge.

Integration is the process of forming integrity from previously isolated one and many components that are different from each other. The consolidation of the content of education means the process and result of the formation of the integrity of knowledge, methods and types of activities, as well as value relations.

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